

Dynamical Mode of Laser Radiation in Quantum Dots Structures with the Optical Stark Effect

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Within the framework of the proposed balance model, the dynamics of stimulated emission in active media, which are characterized by the optical Stark effect, has been studied. It has been shown that the nonlinear shift of resonant transition levels, caused by the optical Stark effect, is an instability factor in the kinetic scheme of the laser. The ranges of values of the excitation (pumping) level and linear resonance detuning were found for which spontaneous transition of stimulated emission to the regime of self-oscillations of intensity is possible. Simulations of the relaxation dynamics of radiation have been carried out for typical parameters of lasers based on semiconductor quantum-sized structures for near-IR range.

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1. Introduction

Intensive development of nanoelectronics and photonics devices is directly related to advances in the growth of quantum-sized structures with certain physical and optical characteristics that allow their use as low-dimensional sources of a coherent light field [1-3]. Semiconductor media with quantum-size effects, which are represented by arrays of quantum dots, are considered promising in this regard [4, 5]. Particular attention is paid to quantum dot lasers capable of generating radiation in the mode of regular oscillations without the use of external modulating components of the device circuit, as they find their application in optical information transmission systems [4]. Under the action of a constant level of excitation, emitted contrast series of periodic light pulsations can be formed due to self-oscillating mechanisms that arise due to the nonlinearity of the response of the amplifying element. A targeted change

in the characteristics of stimulated emission is carried out by a level of constant pumping over time or by the parameters of a compact passive dispersive element in the feedback circuit. Such elements based on structures of quantum dot arrays are characterized by large dipole moments associated with excitonic transitions, amounting to several tens of Debye moments [6]. Submicron and nanometer layers based on such media with a pronounced resonant response to the field of coherent radiation can have a strong resonant nonlinearity; in these objects it is possible to observe coherent optical effects [6 - 8] and nonlinear phase variations of the field acting in the layer. The energy balance of the excitation source, correlating and emitted fields in such a structure can be considered traditionally – within the framework of a two-level diagram of the levels of the resonant particles that form it – quantum emitters (QEs), represented by elementary dipoles. A factor that can play a special role in the development of self-oscillatory processes, provided the dipole moments are relatively large, is the difference in the polarizabilities of the cosmic ray in the ground

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and excited states [9]. The magnitude of the polarizability defect determines the optical Stark effect, that is, a shift in the spectral resonance of the gain, proportional to the intensity. The redistribution of QEs over the levels of the main transition is due to the resonant nonlinearity of the refraction of the amplifying element, the contribution of which to the frequency shift of the stimulated emission field also depends on the polarizability defect and population variation [10 - 12].

The purpose of the study underlying this article was to study the role of both effects of phase nonlinearity in the development of instability of the stimulated emission process. Dynamic instability can lead to the formation of a self-oscillatory structure in the illuminated optical field – the so-called self-sustaining radiation pulsations.

2. Basic equations

Kinetic model of the laser, in which the energy exchange between an amplifying element and the emitted light field of the intensity $E(t)$ with a carrier frequency ω is further described, was based on the commonly used lamped non-stationary scheme (see, for example, [13]). The medium placed in the resonator is formed by dipole QEs, the orientation of which in the direction of the field acting in the structure is characterized by a finite relaxation time. The time of such orientation is characterized by the value T_2 (transverse relaxation time, in semiconductor media – intraband relaxation). This parameter determines time of spontaneous decay of resonant polarization and, in the case of uniform broadening, the size (half-width) of the spectral resonant gain line on the frequency scale. The quasi-stationary expression of complex polarization in the application of a generalized two-level scheme, in addition to the resonant component, contains a quasi-resonant component:

$$P(t) = i\mu_{12}N\rho(t) + 2\pi\varepsilon_0\Delta\alpha N(n_0 - n)E(t). \quad (1)$$

The presence of this component in the representation (1), in accordance with [14], takes into account the difference in polarizability with the defect $\Delta\alpha$ at transition levels. It is called quasi-resonant due to the fact that the difference in polarizabilities α_1 and α_2 in the ground and excited states of the QEs is due to the absorption of radiation in transitions adjacent to the resonant one. The factor of the existence of a defect $\Delta\alpha = \alpha_2 - \alpha_1$ makes it possible to introduce into consideration resonant non-linear refraction, determined by the variation in the difference in the populations of the resonant transition levels n (population inversion). The function (1) includes probabilistic variables of complex polarization ρ and inversion n , the dynamics of which are determined by the quantum mechanical equations of the density matrix, μ_{12} is the modulus of the matrix element of the dipole moment, N is the volumetric density of resonant particles, n_0 is the initial value of the inverse population (henceforth $n_0 = 1$).

Following the approach developed in [15, 16], we choose the calculation scheme in the form of an equation for the average field strength E along the length of the resonator, solved together with a system of quantum mechanical equations for the resonant response of the medium (Bloch equations for the electric moment of the QEs). The proposed modification of the original computing scheme, however, takes into account the representation (1) with the inclusion, similarly to [14], of a nonlinear Stark component in the frequency detuning $\Delta\omega = \omega - \omega_{12}$ (ω_{12} is the resonant amplification frequency):

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dE}{dt} &= \frac{1}{T}(P - \chi E), \\ \frac{d\rho}{dt} &= \frac{\mu_{12}}{\hbar}nE \\ -\rho &\left(\frac{i}{T_2} + \Delta\omega + \frac{\pi\Delta\alpha}{\hbar}\varepsilon_0|E|^2\right), \\ \frac{dn}{dt} &= \frac{n_0 - n}{T_1} - \frac{\mu_{12}}{2\hbar}(\rho^*E + \rho E^*). \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Here T and T_1 are the time the light travels around the resonator and the time of longitudinal

relaxation of the transition (in semiconductor media – interband relaxation), χ is the level of losses due to lasing radiation (as a result of its output from the resonator), as well as absorption and scattering in active layer, T is the time it takes light to travel around the resonator. As a result of the adiabatic exclusion of the variable resonant polarization ρ in the scheme of pump power balance and stimulated emission (2), it is possible to formulate rate equations written for the variables of normalized radiation power $y(\tau)$ and inversion $x(\tau)$ (the latter in the present formulation of the problem is described by the resonant variation of the inverse population n , related to the loss level τ):

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dy}{d\tau} &= \frac{1}{\tau_r} \left(\frac{x+1}{1+\Delta^2} - 1 \right) y, \\ \frac{dx}{d\tau} &= \sigma - x - \frac{x+1}{1+\Delta^2} y, \\ \Delta &= \Delta\omega T_2 - \beta x + \beta\tau_{12} y, \\ y &= \frac{\mu_{12}}{\hbar^2} T_1 T_2 |E|^2, \quad x = \frac{n}{\chi} - 1, \\ \tau &= \frac{t}{T_1}, \quad \beta = \frac{2\pi\varepsilon_0\hbar}{\mu^2 T_2} \Delta\alpha. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

In the system (3), it is convenient to normalize the time variable by parameter T_1 . The value $|E|^2$ that determines the normalized power y is related to the inversion saturation power, the value τ_r (the lifetime of a photon in the resonator, also normalized by the T_1 parameter), in addition to losses in the resonator, takes into account the values of the resonator fill factor and the optical limitation parameter; To take pump into account, the parameter $\sigma = n_0/\chi - 1$ was introduced, characterizing the maximum achievable gain at a given excitation level (outside the pump current). Normalized by the width of the gain line, the frequency detuning Δ with the adiabatic exclusion of the variable, in addition to the linear component $\Delta\omega T_2$, includes a term that is determined by the frequency drift due to nonlinear refraction with a proportionality coefficient β (in essence, which is a parameter of amplitude-phase coupling). It is also important that the nonlinear part of the detuning includes the Stark component, proportional to the power

$y(\tau)$ with the normalizing parameter $\tau_{12} = T_2/2T_1$.

Taking into account the factor $\Delta\alpha$ and the optical Stark effect, based on (3), the influence of a shift in the resonant transition levels in an intense light field on the stability of the stimulated emission process can be assessed. In semiconductor media, the amplitude-phase coupling parameter is then proportional to the well-known Henry factor [17]. Under the conditions of the effectiveness of this factor, the gain in the quantum-dimensional structure acquires a dynamic phase-modulation component, being linearly dependent on the rate of change in the QEs concentration with a coefficient proportional to the parameter β .

3. Stability of solutions and self-oscillation mode

The rate equations (3) take into account a number of nonlinear effects that are possible under dynamic scenarios of the development of stimulated emission in structures made of QEs, which include excitons or quantum dots in semiconductors used in laser optics.

A qualitative study of the behavior of solutions for $y(\tau)$ near an equilibrium state with non-zero power y_S first of all makes it possible to estimate the zone of parameters of the system (3) in which this state is stable [13] – on the time scale, curves that describe solutions for both variables, leaving from the initial points, after a series of oscillations they decay to equilibrium values. Expressions for the equilibrium states x_S, y_S follow from the singular limits of the system (3):

$$\sigma = x_S + y_S, \quad \beta\tau_{12}y_S = \Delta\omega T_2 + \beta x_S \pm \sqrt{x_S}. \quad (4)$$

Linearization of system (3) in the vicinity of the equilibrium points (4) allows us to write an analogue of the balance scheme (3) for relatively small solutions $\Delta x(\tau)$ and $\Delta y(\tau)$ in a certain region of the phase plane (x, y) , including points x_S, y_S . The linearized analogue of the circuit

is represented as a system of linear differential equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_r \frac{d\Delta y}{d\tau} &= -2\beta\tau_{12}y_S \frac{\sqrt{x_S}}{1+x_S} \Delta y \\ &+ \frac{y_S}{1+x_S} (1 - 2\beta\sqrt{x_S}) \Delta x, \\ \frac{d\Delta x}{d\tau} &= \left(2\beta\tau_{12}y_S \frac{\sqrt{x_S}}{1+x_S} - 1 \right) \Delta y \\ &- \left[1 + \frac{y_S}{1+x_S} (1 - 2\beta\sqrt{x_S}) \right] \Delta x. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Based on Eqs. (5), a characteristic polynomial is formulated with respect to λ being the complex damping coefficient in the exponential solution exponent $\exp(\lambda\tau)$ of the system (5). Oscillating solutions are the most realistic, but if the oscillations are clearly relaxing, that is, they decay to equilibrium values, system (3) describes the transition of the laser to a steady state, that is, stationary, radiation mode. The equilibrium point x_S, y_S on the phase plane (x, y) of system (3) then represents a stable focus and is an attractor of phase curves. The characteristic polynomial, expressed as a quadratic equation, must have complex conjugate roots $\lambda_{1,2} = (\kappa \pm i\sqrt{-D})/2$.

Expressions for the real part of the roots and the discriminant of the characteristic equation are written as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \kappa &= -\frac{1}{2} \left(1 + A - \beta \frac{\tau_{12}}{\tau_r} B \right), \\ D &= \left(1 + A - \beta \frac{\tau_{12}}{\tau_r} B \right)^2 - \frac{4}{\tau_r} (A - \beta\tau_{12}B), \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where

$$A = \frac{\sigma - x_S}{1+x_S} (1 - 2\beta\sqrt{x_S}), \quad B = 2 \frac{\sigma - x_S}{1+x_S} \sqrt{x_S},$$

and together with the relations (4) can be used as the basis for a criterion for characterizing the behavior of trajectories on the phase plane (x, y) in the vicinity of the equilibrium state x_S, y_S . Stability of the focus x_S, y_S is possible under the condition $\kappa < 0$. The representation of the quantities κ and D in the expressions (6) by the functions x_S is convenient for subsequent

parametric calculations of dependencies of the type $\kappa(\sigma)$. The variable value x_S is considered to be a non-negative parameter that linearly increases over a certain range.

Obviously, when determining the conditions for the formation of self-oscillations, it is necessary to identify zones of parameters where points x_S, y_S are unstable like an unstable focus. The departure of trajectories corresponding to the oscillatory solutions (3) from the neighborhood of the equilibrium point should mean that their attractor will be a limit cycle. This is due to the inevitable periodic saturation of the growth $x(\tau)$ with an increase in the stimulated emission power $y(\tau)$ with a subsequent decrease (inversion reset). The equilibrium point turns out to be an unstable focus if $\kappa > 0$. This kind of instability corresponds to a periodic solution with frequency $\Omega = \sqrt{-D}/2$ for linearized equations. The original system (3) is characterized by oscillatory solutions for $x(\tau)$ and $y(\tau)$, the amplitudes of which are stabilized. Thus, the proposed model describes the development of a scenario of regular undamped pulsations. The self-oscillatory radiation mode, realized at a constant pump level, is interesting from a practical point of view. Therefore, using the condition of instability of the focus, we indicate the boundary of its feasibility, applying for this the first of relations (6):

$$\sigma > x_S + (1+x_S) \left[1 + 2\beta \left(1 - \frac{\tau_{12}}{\tau_r} \right) \sqrt{x_S} \right]. \quad (7)$$

When assessing condition (7), it is necessary to take into account the second of relations (4).

The significance of condition (7) is conveniently illustrated on the scale of the excitation parameter σ for different frequency detuning values (Figure 1a). The value of the points of intersection of the curves $\kappa(\sigma)$ with the horizontal axis then determines the so-called second generation threshold (pumping level σ , starting from which spontaneous instability of stimulated emission is possible). However, instability must be realized in a certain range of changes in σ , which increases with a larger value of the factor $\Delta\alpha$. The instability exhibits

a dispersion dependence, developing in a certain range of linear resonance tuning (Figure 1b).

Numerical modeling based on the system of equations (3), as well as calculation of threshold characteristics based on Eqs. (4) and (6), were carried out for the parameters of quantum-sized structures taken from literature sources and most actively studied recently for use in as an elemental base for nanophotonics [4, 18, 19]. When assessing the scale of the predicted phenomena, we proceeded approximately from the parameters of quantum-sized lasers for the QEs structure in the InAs/(Al)GaAs system on GaAs substrates, emitting, depending on the concentration of quantum dots and the level of optical losses, in the wavelength range 1.25–1.29 μm .

4. Modeling of relaxation dynamics of radiation

Calculations of radiation processes were based on numerical integration of the kinetic system (3) using the Runge-Kutta method. The initial conditions corresponded to the fulfillment of the amplitude generation condition $x(\tau = 0) = x_S$. The initial value $y(\tau = 0)$ is several orders of magnitude less than the equilibrium value. That is, at the initial stage of modeling the development of the stimulated emission process, the problem of amplifying a weak signal was solved. The scans of the dynamic pattern of stimulated emission for variable power $y(t)$, obtained by modeling the process, in Figures 2 and 3 are shown in the nanosecond time range. Figure 2 illustrates two main variants of the solution scenario: transitional (after a decaying series of bursts $y(t)$) to a steady state with continuous power (Figure 2, a, b, f) and self-oscillatory in the form of a periodic sequence of contrasting picosecond pulses (Figures 2c, 2d, 2e). The conditions for the occurrence of a self-oscillatory mode correspond to the relation (7). Fragments of Figure 2 differ in the values of the excitation parameter σ , which correspond to

points on the scale $\Delta\omega T_2$ for curve 2 of Figure 1b.

Figure 3 illustrates the characteristic modeling results, which make it possible to compare the development of the oscillatory process in stimulated emission as the dynamics of the variables x, y , firstly, under the conditions of fully taking into account all nonlinear modulation mechanisms (Figure 3a), and secondly, under the conditions neglecting factors causing instability of the radiation process (Figures 3b, 3c).

The difference in the dependencies in the fragments of Figure 3 indicates that self-oscillations of the inverse population and power develop when the influence of the optical Stark effect is taken into account. It is the resonance shift due to the optical Stark effect that is the destabilizing factor, and only under these conditions is a series of regular undamped pulses formed (Figure 3a). The phase effect of nonlinear refraction, which leads to a shift in the field frequency when the QEs is redistributed among transition levels, is not capable of exerting a decisive modulating effect (Figure 3b). The numerical solutions (3), as in the case of the complete absence of phase nonlinearity (Figure 3c), describe the transition to a stationary radiation mode, the inverse population stabilizes at the threshold gain level.

Figure 4 illustrates the sweep of radiation pulsations for increasing values of linear resonance detuning and corresponding curves on the phase plane (x, y) . Fragments of Figure 4 differ in the values of linear resonance detuning $\Delta\omega T_2$, which correspond to points on the scale $\Delta\omega T_2$ for curve 3 from Figure 1b.

In the laser radiation, transient modes with access to stationary emitted power are possible (Figures 4a, 4e, 4f); phase trajectories enter the vicinity of singular points at different rates. The mode of self-sustaining pulsations during continuous pumping exists in a certain range of resonance detuning (Figure 4b–d), phase trajectories have a limit cycle as an attractor (Figures 4b’–d’). With an increase in the initial resonance detuning, the duty cycle and peak amplitude of pulsations may increase,

FIG. 1. Dependencies of the real part of the roots of the characteristic equation on the excitation level (pumping) and linear frequency detuning from the gain resonance. The parameters are $\beta = 0.1$ (1), 0.15 (2), 0.18 (3), $\Delta\omega T_2 = 0.5$ (a); $\sigma = 1.6$ (1), 2.0 (2), 2.4 (3), $\beta = 0.15$ (b); $\tau_{12} = 1.0 \cdot 10^{-2}$.

FIG. 2. Oscillations of the normalized power of stimulated radiation. The parameters are $\sigma = 1.2$ (a), 1.3 (b), 1.4 (c), 2.0 (d), 2.5 (e), 3.2 (f), $\beta = 0.15$, $\Delta\omega T_2 = 0.5$, $\tau_r = 7 \cdot 10^{-3}$, $\tau_{12} = 1.0 \cdot 10^{-2}$.

FIG. 3. Oscillations of the normalized power of stimulated radiation against the background of relative fluctuations in population inversion (dashed curves) for the following parameters: $\beta = 0.12$ (a, c), 0.0 (b), $\tau_{12} = 7.2 \times 10^{-3}$ (a), 0.0 (b, c), $\sigma = 2.4$, $\Delta\omega T_2 = 0.5$, $\tau_r = 7 \cdot 10^{-3}$.

FIG. 4. Oscillations of the normalized power of stimulated emission (a-f) for the following parameters: $\Delta\omega T_2 = 0.33$ (a, a'), 0.6 (b, b'), 0.7 (c, c'), 0.75 (d, d'), 0.8 (e, e'), 1.0 (f, f'), $\sigma = 2.4$, $\beta = 0.15$ (b); $\tau_{12} = 1.0 \cdot 10^{-2}$, corresponding phase trajectories (a'-f').

and their duration may decrease. This can be explained by the fact that the level of modulation increases – with an initially shifted resonance, the inversion increases to a greater extent (until the threshold lasing conditions are met). The change in inversion due to the frequency shift becomes particularly unstable, while the transition to the self-oscillation mode requires rather insignificant self-modulation oscillations of the inversion and the associated amplification [13]. Then, during the development phase of stimulated emission, nonlinear restructuring returns the response of the medium to a state closer to resonance, so as a result, a more powerful and shorter pulse is formed. In a certain range of phase detuning values, this process is characterized by regularity, then undamped periodic self-oscillations are maintained in stimulated emission.

5. Conclusion

Resonant generation model proposed in the work takes into account the influence

of the phase rearrangement of the material response of the medium on a radiation field due to Stark shift of the amplification resonance. The generation model allows to describe the process of the development of self-oscillations of radiation, which can be realized in quantum-sized semiconductor structures and to determine the regime of self-sustaining luminescence pulsations. Taking into account the Stark shift factor and its ability to stimulate the self-modulation process when calculating real sources of coherent radiation seems to be of fundamental importance. It can be assumed that the nonlinear refraction observed in quantum-sized structures is a consequence of the redistribution of resonant QEs among transition levels with differences in polarizability. Then the optical Stark effect turns out to be significant, which determines additional instability of the interaction scheme, with a typical nonlinearity coefficient that also depends on the polarizability defect.

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